

Peer Review Journal

ISSN 1817-5562

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine

The Official Journal of The Iraqi Ministry of Health

Volume 2 Number 1 March 2006

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

Executive Editor: Ali Hassan Al Shimari
Minister of Health

Founding Editor: Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi
Member World Association of Medical Editors

Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index Medicus

Copyright Iraqi Ministry of Health

Double extensor pollicis longus muscle and its clinical significance

Srijit Das, Associate Professor

Department of Anatomy, Maulana Azad Medical College

190 RPS Flats, Sheikh Sarai Phase-I. New Delhi-110017 India

Tel: 91-11-9811974702

E-mail: das_srijit23@rediffmail.com.

Rajesh Suri ,Professor

Department of Anatomy, Vardhman Mahavir Medical College

New Delhi, India.

Vijay Kapur, Former Director Professor & HOD

Department of Anatomy, Maulana Azad Medical College, New Delhi, India

Abstract

Background: The Extensor Pollicis Longus (EPL) is an important muscle producing the extension of the thumb. There are few reports on double EPL muscle in literature. The present study reports the presence of double EPL muscle with its morphological description and also highlights its clinical significance.

Materials and Methods: We dissected 50 upper limbs in the department of anatomy to observe the variations of the extensor muscles of the forearm. The anomaly of double EPL was studied in detail and appropriate photograph was taken.

Results: Double EPL muscle was observed in a left upper limb of a 37 year old male cadaver. The two muscles had its origin from the posterior surface of the shaft of the ulna and interosseous membrane and displayed a common insertion into the base of distal phalanx of the thumb.

Conclusion: The presence of double EPL muscle may be important for academic purpose and clinical studies considering the fact that EPL tendon is

used for tendon transfer. The prior knowledge of such anomalies may be important during Surgeries for hand trauma.

Key Words: Extensor Pollicis Longus, double, accessory, tendon, anomaly, variations, abnormalities.

Introduction

The EPL muscle has been known to exhibit variations. Interestingly, the incidence of the variations of the extensor tendons has been found to be less common on the radial side than on the ulnar side [1]. There are some reports on the presence of double EPL muscle [2,3]. Variations of EPL may be in the form of an individual muscle belly

which may completely separate from the common extensor tendons having a proper tendinous insertion [4]. It is often necessary to be aware of the anatomical previous research study had described accessory EPL tendon in a patient which resulted in wrist pain [6]. Considering the fact that an incidence of 26% cases having double EPL tendons have been reported, the clinical importance of this anomaly cannot be neglected [7]. A previous research report had described an accessory EPL located between the normal EPL and the Extensor Indicis Proprius muscle [8]. The anatomical knowledge of such anomalous muscle may be important for surgeons. The present study describes in detail a case of double EPL muscle and discusses its clinical significance. Awareness of the normal and abnormal topographical anatomy of the extensor muscles of the hand may be important during tendoplasty, tendon transfer operations and during decompression for the treatment of de Quervain's tenosynovitis.

Materials and Methods

Fifty upper limbs from formalin fixed cadavers in the Anatomy dissection hall were taken for the study. The extensor compartment of the forearm was dissected. The tendons of these muscles were displayed and studied in detail. Any anomalies were looked for and appropriate photograph was taken (Fig.1).

Results

Double EPL muscle was observed in the left upper limb of a 37 year old male cadaver. There were two muscle bellies of EPL (marked as 'a' & 'b' in Fig.1).

variations of the extensor tendons while performing tendon transfer and treating traumatized hand [5]. A

One originated from the posterior surface of the shaft of ulna and the other from interosseous membrane. These two slender muscle bellies became tendinous, about 4 cm proximal to the wrist. The two tendons traversed deep to the extensor retinaculum and were found to unite at the dorsum of proximal phalanx of the thumb to be inserted into the distal phalanx.

Discussion

Standard anatomy textbooks do not mention in detail the incidence of anomalies of EPL especially double EPL muscle. There are reports of supplementary extensor tendons of the hand [2, 9, 10, 11]. It may be an individual muscle belly separated from the common extensor tendons having an additional insertion as an additional tendon [4]. Interestingly, the anomalies of the extensor tendons have been found more on the radial side compared to the ulnar side [1]. In the present study also, the anomaly involves the EPL muscle which is on the radial side of the forearm. The variations of extensor tendons of the thumb have been reported while performing operations and cadaver dissections [12]. On extensive review of literature we encountered two cases of double EPL tendon [2, 3]. There are also reports of abnormal origin and insertion of extensors of the thumb [13, 14, 15]. In the present case, the muscle originated as two separate bellies, traversed deep to the extensor retinaculum to be inserted as a single tendon into the base of the distal phalanx. Additional extensor of the thumb, having their own origin,

insertion and separate belly is an extremely rare entity[16]. Such anomalous muscles may be incidental finding during cadaver dissection or developmental in origin. It has been suggested that an accessory long extensor tendon to the thumb may be regarded as a primitive remnant [1].

A previous researcher had stated that phylogenetically the accessory EPL in human beings can be traced to primates [18]. The explanation for such anomalies may be related to a shift of the deep extensor sheet of muscle to the radial side as seen in rhesus monkeys and baboons [1].

Conclusion

The presence of two tendons of EPL could be physiological advantage in case of injury to one. It has been documented earlier that rupture of the EPL may be associated with chronic tenosynovitis caused by repetitive activity [19]. The awareness of the variations of the extensor tendons is important while decompressing the compartment for de Quervain's tenosynovitis [10]. We as anatomists opine that awareness of anomalous extensor muscles of the hand may be important for surgeons while carrying out reconstructive procedures in the hand region.

Acknowledgement: The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. Aamir Al Mosawi Honorable Editor, The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine for the excellent support.

References

1-Straus WL: The phylogeny of the human forearm extensors Human Biol 1941; 13: 23-50.

operations. The anomalous course of EPL muscle has been reported to be associated with pain [17]. The presence of double EPL could be

2-Mc Gregor AL: A contribution to the morphology of the thumb. J Anat 1926;60: 266- 269.

3- Wood J: On some variations in human myology. Proc R Soc London 1867; 15 : 518- 546.

4- Jones BV: An anomalous extensor indicis muscle. J Bone Joint Surg 1959 ;41B: 763-765.

5-von Schroeder HP, Botte MJ : Anatomy of the extensor tendons of the fingers: variations and multiplicity. J Hand Surg [Am]. 1995; 20: 27-34.

6-Beatty JD, Remedios D, McCullough CJ : An accessory extensor tendon of the thumb as a cause of dorsal wrist pain. J Hand Surg [Br]. 2000; 25: 110-1.

7-Yoshida Y : Anatomical study on the extensor digitorum profundus muscle in the Japanese. Okajimas Folia Anat Jpn.1990; 66: 339-53.

8-Cohen BE, Haber JL : Supernumerary extensor tendon to the thumb: a case report. Ann Plast Surg. 1996; 36: 105-7.

9-Aydinlioglu A, Tosun N, Keles P, Akpınar F, Diyarbakirli S : Variations of abductor pollicis longus and extensor pollicis brevis muscles: surgical significance. Kaibogaku Zasshi. 1998; 73: 19-23

10-Gonzalez MH, Sohlberg R, Brown A, Weinzwieg N : The first dorsal extensor

compartment: an anatomic study. J Hand

11-Schenk R: Variations on the extensor tendons of the fingers: surgical significance. J Bone Joint Surg [Am] 1964; 46:103–110.

12-Martinez R, Omer GE Jr : Bilateral subluxation of the base of the thumb secondary to an unusual abductor pollicis longus insertion: a case report. J Hand Surg [Am]. 1985; 10: 396-9.

13- Cauldwell EW, Anson BJ, and R.R.Wright : The extensor indicis Proprius muscle. A study of 263 consecutive specimens. Q. Bull. Northwestern Univ.Med. School 1943; 17: 267-279.

14- Macalister A: Note on muscular anomalies in human anatomy. Proceedings of the Royal Irish Academy 1866 ; 9 : 444-467.

15- Stein AH: Variations of the tendons of insertion of the abductor pollicis longus and the extensor pollicis brevis. Anat Rec. 1951 ;110 : 49-55.

16-Abu-Hijleh MF : Extensor pollicis tertius: an additional extensor muscle to the thumb. Plast Reconstr Surg. 1993;92: 340-3. Orthop Relat Res 1997; 345 :171-173.

Surg [Am]. 1995; 20: 657-60.

17-Nishijo K, Kotani H, Miki T, Senzoku F, Ueo T : Unusual course of the extensor pollicis longus tendon associated with tenosynovitis, presenting as de Quervain disease--a case report. Acta Orthop Scand. 2000; 71 : 426-8.

18-Papaloizos MY: Accessory extensor pollicis longus. Scand J Plast Reconstr Surg Hand Surg. 2004; 38: 310-3.

19- Adler Louis, Blazar Philip ,Lee ong : Acute Attenuation of the Extensor Pollicis Longus Tendon: A Case Report. Clin

Figure (1): Photograph of dissected specimen showing two muscle bellies of Extensor Pollicis Longus arrows (a) and (b).